

The Impact of the Optimized Surface Sterilization Protocol on Phytochemical Availability in Leaf and Nodal Explants of *Atlantia Ceylanica*: A Tissue Culture-Based Study

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Abstract

Atlantia ceylanica, a renowned Sri Lankan medicinal plant, is widely used in traditional treatments, particularly for diabetes and respiratory disorders. This study aimed to optimize a surface sterilization protocol for leaf and nodal explants and to compare the phytochemical availability between surface-sterilized and non-sterilized tissues. The research was conducted at the Faculty of Science, Horizon Campus, using plant tissue culture techniques. Optimized explant sterilization protocol, includes rinsing the explants with 10–15% Clorox for 15 minutes followed by 70% ethanol for 1 minute. The optimized sterilization protocol successfully reduced contamination from 10% to 0% in nodal explants and from 8% to 0% in leaf explants, enabling the establishment of viable cultures. Shoot initiation reached 70% on hormone-free Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium. Preliminary phytochemical screening was performed using sequential extraction with hexane, ethyl acetate, and methanol. Alkaloids and phenols were predominantly observed in nodal tissues, while flavonoids, tannins, and saponins were more abundant in leaf tissues. Alkaloids and phenolic compounds were detected in 80% of surface-sterilized nodes, whereas 75% of non-sterilized leaves showed flavonoids and tannins. No terpenoids were detected in any treatment. Further, replicates and the quantitative phytochemical analysis are required to validate and expand these preliminary findings, contributing to standardized propagation and phytochemical profiling of *A. ceylanica*.

Keywords: *Atlantia ceylanica*, Surface sterilization, Phytochemical analysis